

TAARA-Based Network Forensics Approach for Detecting Slowloris Application-Layer DoS Attack

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Abstract—With the increasing internet penetration in Indonesia, the threat of cyberattacks has escalated, particularly Denial of Service (DoS) attacks such as Slowloris, which operate at the application layer and are difficult to detect due to their resemblance to legitimate traffic. Previous studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of the TAARA (Trigger, Acquire, Analyze, Report, Action) framework in handling various cyber incidents; however, its application to Slowloris attacks remains underexplored. This study aims to implement and evaluate the TAARA framework within the context of digital forensic investigations targeting Slowloris attacks, while also assessing its alignment with core principles of network forensics. An experimental simulation-based approach was employed, involving five distinct Slowloris attack scenarios, each tested three times (a total of 15 experiments). Data were collected from an intrusion detection system (Suricata), web server logs (Apache2), and network traffic captures (PCAP). The investigation process adhered comprehensively to the TAARA workflow, from initial trigger to recommendation formulation. Evaluation was conducted based on four fundamental aspects in digital forensics practice: legal acceptability, data integrity, repeatability, and effectiveness. The TAARA framework demonstrated its effectiveness in guiding forensic investigations of Slowloris attacks, from initial detection to mitigation actions. In one scenario, over 5,207 alerts were recorded within five minutes, with 26,576 transmitted packets averaging 105 bytes in size. The attack characteristics were consistently reflected in log patterns, particularly the dominance of HTTP 408 (Request Timeout) responses from the target server. These findings were supported by eve.json logs, packet capture files, and server access records, all indicating distinctive traces of application-layer attacks. In addition to enabling systematic documentation of digital evidence, the TAARA approach facilitates attack pattern identification and the development of mitigation strategies such as connection throttling and IP blocking, reinforcing its relevance and replicability in digital forensic investigations.

Keywords—Slowloris attack, TAARA framework, network forensics, Suricata IDS, digital evidence

I. INTRODUCTION

In the current digital era, the internet has become a primary necessity for the Indonesian population. According to data from the Indonesian Internet Service Providers Association (APJII), internet penetration in 2024 reached 79.50% of the total population [1]. This figure indicates a high level of information technology adoption across various segments of society, including students, the workforce, and business actors.

The increasing number of internet users aligns with the growing coverage of network infrastructure, spanning personal, private organizational, and government institutional scales. Easier access to network infrastructure has brought

various positive impacts, including facilitating communication, education, and professional activities. However, this convenience also entails consequences, namely an increased risk of cyberattacks that can lead to significant losses.

Ransomware causes damage more often

Which of the following types of cyber attacks have caused damage to your company in the last 12 months?

Fig. 1. Trends In Cyber Attacks From 2022 To 2024.

Data indicate an upward trend in cyberattacks over the past three years, with ransomware, phishing, password attacks, and Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) emerging as the primary threats [2]. As illustrated in Fig. 1, ransomware attacks have consistently ranked at the top, followed by phishing and DDoS attacks, both of which have shown an increasing trend year over year. Interestingly, DDoS attacks have consistently ranked among the top five most damaging attack types, in line with findings that report a significant surge in application-layer protocol attacks [3].

One notable variant of DDoS that warrants concern is the Slowloris attack. Unlike conventional flooding methods, Slowloris targets servers by sending partial HTTP requests and maintaining connections over extended periods. This technique gradually exhausts server resources using minimal bandwidth. As the traffic closely resembles legitimate requests, this type of attack is difficult to detect yet highly effective in disabling web-based services [4].

The impact of such activities is reflected in the Incident Response Analyst Report 2024, which notes that 10.1% of all confirmed incidents were caused by suspicious network activity, and 42.9% of false alarms also stemmed from abnormal traffic patterns, such as those employed in Slowloris attacks [5]. Therefore, precise investigative techniques are essential to differentiate legitimate from suspicious traffic.

In this context, digital forensics plays a critical role in identifying and verifying traces of cyberattacks. Digital forensics is a field focused on the recovery and investigation of digital data to support law enforcement in combating

cybercrime. Its branches include live, network, computer, mobile, and database forensics [6]. This process is carried out systematically using specialized techniques and analytical tools to produce valid and legally admissible digital evidence.

As incident complexity increases, selecting an appropriate investigative approach becomes crucial for effective analysis. In response to these challenges, structured and repeatable frameworks are essential. One such proven method is the TAARA approach Trigger, Acquire, Analyze, Report, and Action. TAARA has been applied in various cases, such as ARP spoofing and ransomware, utilizing tools like Wireshark and NetworkMiner [7], [8]. This approach facilitates a structured process for tracking and analyzing digital evidence, from incident triggers to post-investigation actions.

The TAARA method offers distinct advantages in guiding investigators to observe early symptoms, collect relevant data, and compile accurate reports. In this study, the TAARA approach will be applied to explore the characteristics of Slowloris application-layer attacks in greater depth. The primary focus is on how this method can effectively identify attacks that mimic legitimate traffic, a persistent challenge in detecting and mitigating application-layer Denial of Service (DoS) attacks.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The advancement of information technology has accelerated the development of digital systems, while simultaneously increasing cybersecurity risks. One of the more elusive threats is the Denial of Service (DoS) attack, particularly Slowloris, which exploits incomplete HTTP connections to cripple a server using only a single machine and minimal bandwidth [4], [9]. In this context, digital forensics—especially network forensics—plays a crucial role in post-incident analysis and the disclosure of legally admissible digital evidence. Digital forensics is a scientific process involving the collection, preservation, analysis, and presentation of digital evidence to support legal proceedings [10], wherein the principle of chain of custody is essential in maintaining the integrity of evidence throughout the investigation [11].

Network forensics enables investigators to reconstruct incidents by analyzing data traffic and system logs. Tools such as Wireshark assist in detecting abnormal traffic patterns, including the slow connections typical of Slowloris attacks [12], while Suricata is utilized to identify attack patterns through signature-based detection [13], [14]. The National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) framework serves as a standard reference in investigations, comprising four core phases: Collection, Examination, Analysis, and Reporting [15], which are widely applicable and flexible for handling cyber incidents.

This study simulates a Slowloris attack on a web server using a laboratory-based approach and analyzes the results using digital forensic methods. The data sources include traffic captures, server access logs, and alerts from intrusion detection systems, which are analyzed to identify attack characteristics. The obtained digital evidence is validated and documented to ensure compliance with forensic standards and admissibility in legal processes [16].

The TAARA method is applied in this study as a foundational framework for conducting the investigation,

with a detailed breakdown presented in Section 4. As illustrated in Fig. 2, TAARA comprises a sequence of phases.

Fig. 2. The TAARA Method.

The following is a brief description of the interrelation between each step in the TAARA method, as illustrated in Fig. 2.

1. Trigger refers to an event that occurs following an attack and prompts investigators to initiate the forensic process.
2. Acquire involves gathering all available information and evidence to determine the origin of the attack incident.
3. Analysis is the process of assembling and correlating the collected evidence and information to raise questions or concerns regarding the ongoing attack.
4. Report entails compiling a report based on the preceding analysis, documenting all activities involved in the investigation.
5. Action represents the stage in which steps or recommendations are taken based on the findings outlined in the report.

This research framework consists of eight stages, incorporating the TAARA method as a core component, and concludes with an evaluation phase. The sequence of these stages is visually depicted in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Research Process Flow Diagram.

As illustrated in Fig. 3, the initial phase begins with a literature review aimed at gathering relevant information from prior sources that support this research. This is followed by the determination of attack scenarios, which are implemented using the available tools and materials. The investigation process is then carried out by applying the stages of the TAARA method, beginning with the Trigger phase and continuing through to Action. Finally, the evaluation phase is conducted by assessing the outcomes derived from applying the TAARA method following the network forensic process.

A. Requirement Resources

The attack scenario is constructed by preparing the necessary hardware and software components required for testing purposes. The complete list of these components is presented in Table I.

TABLE I. HARDWARE AND SOFTWARE REQUIREMENTS

No	Hardware dan Software	Description
1	ZTE ZXHN F670L GPON ONT Router	Network Interconnect Device

2	MacBook Pro (13-inch, M1, 2020), RAM 8GB	Host Virtual Machine
3	Ubuntu 22.0.4	Operating System
4	Kali Linux 2025.1	
5	UTM 4.6.5	Virtual Machine
6	slowloris.py	Slowloris Attack Tool
7	Suricata 7.0.10	Slowloris Detection Tool
8	Apache/2.4.52 (Ubuntu)	Web Server
9	Wireshark 4.4.6	Forensic Tool
10	Tcpdump 4.99.1	

B. Network Design

This network was built using infrastructure deployed in a local network environment. The detailed topology is illustrated in Fig. 4 below.

Fig. 4. Network Topology.

Fig. 4 illustrates the simulated attack topology within a local network, utilizing two virtual machines connected via bridged mode to a router (192.168.1.1). The attacker machine, assigned the IP address 192.168.1.9, performs testing on the victim machine at IP address 192.168.1.8,

Fig. 5. Flow of the Slowloris Attack Simulation.

which runs the Apache web service. The connection scenario is specifically designed to observe the system's response to network activity.

To support this process, tcpdump was utilized during the simulation to monitor and capture network traffic in real time. Since all devices operate within the same network segment, this tool proves effective in comprehensively and accurately

recording host-to-host communications. The detailed test configuration is presented in Table II.

TABLE II. IP DETAILS OF THE NETWORK TOPOLOGY

Device	Vlan	IP Address	Gateway
Router	1	192.168.1.1	-
Attacker	1	192.168.1.9	192.168.1.1
Host	1	192.168.1.2	192.168.1.1
Victim	1	192.168.1.8	192.168.1.1

Table II presents the logical address configuration used in the laboratory network. The router functions as the central gateway, while the victim system is equipped with Suricata to detect attacks and generate alerts based on predefined rules.

```

ubuntu@ubuntu: ~
#dos
alert tcp any any -> any 80 (msg: "Possible DDoS attack"; flags: S; flow: stateless; threshold: type both, track by_dst, count 200, seconds 1; sid:10000003; rev:1;)

#slowloris
alert tcp any any -> any 80 (msg: "SlowLoris.py DoS attempt"; flow:established, to_server, no_stream; content: "X-a."; detection_filter:track by_dst, count 50, seconds 30; classtype:denial-of-service; sid:10000004; rev:1;)
12,0-1 90%

```

Fig. 6. Suricata Rules.

As illustrated in Figure 6, the system triggers an alert when it detects at least 50 TCP connection attempts to port 80 within a 30-second interval, particularly if the request pattern contains the string "X-a.". This rule is specifically designed as part of a denial-of-service (DoS) detection mechanism to monitor abnormal incoming traffic targeting the server [14]. All triggered alerts are automatically logged in the system for further forensic analysis.

C. Attack Simulation

The attack simulation was conducted based on the network topology design shown in Fig. 4. A total of 15 test iterations were performed, with the execution details described as follows.

Fig. 5 illustrates the simulation flow of the attack using the Slowloris tool across five different scenarios. Each scenario was tested three times, resulting in a total of 15 experiments with variations in the number of connections, time intervals, and attack durations.

D. Evaluation

The evaluation was conducted to assess the effectiveness of the TAARA approach in the digital forensic investigation of Slowloris attacks. The assessment is based on general principles of digital forensics and refers to four key aspects to ensure the reliability and validity of the investigation results:

- **Legal Acceptability:** Evidence is clearly documented, and the chain of custody is maintained in a simplified yet traceable manner.
- **Data Integrity:** Digital data remains intact and is validated through checksum verification and audit logs.
- **Repeatability:** The TAARA method demonstrates consistency in producing similar findings under identical testing scenarios.
- **Effectiveness:** TAARA successfully identifies attack patterns and produces relevant and actionable analysis.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Trigger

The initial phase in a network forensic investigation is known as the Trigger. In this case, the trigger is marked by the appearance of alerts from the Suricata system, which detected indications of a Slowloris attack, as described in Section II-B. Fig. 6 shows a log excerpt from the fast.log file, where Suricata identifies the suspicious activity as a SlowLoris.py DoS attempt.

```

ubunt... x ub... x ub... x ub... x ub... x ub... x ub... x
Every 2.0s: tail /var/log/suricata/fast.log  ubuntu: Tue May 20 14:31:30 2025
05/20/2025-14:31:17.599771  [**] [1:10000004:1] SlowLoris.py DoS attempt [**] [C
lassification: Detection of a Denial of Service Attack] [Priority: 2] [TCP] 192.168.1.9:60384 -> 192.168.1.8:80
05/20/2025-14:31:17.599771  [**] [1:10000005:1] Potential Slowloris DoS Attack [
**] [Classification: Attempted Denial of Service] [Priority: 2] [TCP] 192.168.1.9:60384 -> 192.168.1.8:80
05/20/2025-14:31:17.599771  [**] [1:10000004:1] SlowLoris.py DoS attempt [**] [C
lassification: Detection of a Denial of Service Attack] [Priority: 2] [TCP] 192.168.1.9:60386 -> 192.168.1.8:80
05/20/2025-14:31:17.599771  [**] [1:10000005:1] Potential Slowloris DoS Attack [
**] [Classification: Attempted Denial of Service] [Priority: 2] [TCP] 192.168.1.9:60386 -> 192.168.1.8:80
05/20/2025-14:31:17.599771  [**] [1:10000004:1] SlowLoris.py DoS attempt [**] [C
lassification: Detection of a Denial of Service Attack] [Priority: 2] [TCP] 192.168.1.9:60398 -> 192.168.1.8:80
05/20/2025-14:31:17.599771  [**] [1:10000005:1] Potential Slowloris DoS Attack [
**] [Classification: Attempted Denial of Service] [Priority: 2] [TCP] 192.168.1.9:60398 -> 192.168.1.8:80
05/20/2025-14:31:17.600302  [**] [1:10000004:1] SlowLoris.py DoS attempt [**] [C
lassification: Detection of a Denial of Service Attack] [Priority: 2] [TCP] 192.168.1.9:60408 -> 192.168.1.8:80
05/20/2025-14:31:17.600302  [**] [1:10000005:1] Potential Slowloris DoS Attack [

```

Fig. 7. Example of an Alert Triggered by a Slowloris Attack.

Fig. 7 displays Suricata’s detection of activity classified as a Denial-of-Service (DoS) attack. The log shows a TCP connection from IP address 192.168.1.9 to the target 192.168.1.8 on port 80. This example of a Slowloris alert represents the prior 14 attack simulations, all of which produced similar responses and outcomes—namely, the successful detection of the Slowloris attack by the system.

B. Acquire

Following the trigger phase indicated by the Suricata alert, the next step involves collecting relevant data. This data acquisition process is carried out through network traffic monitoring and system log recording, as previously discussed in Section II-B, including the use of tcpdump and the eve.json file generated as Suricata’s output log.

TABLE III. EXAMPLE OF DATA COLLECTED FOR EACH SCENARIO

Scenario	File	SHA256 Hash
Light Scenario	eve.json	17820bddde527baf4b33d0a7abd48bc640aa35aca488140b966c73fa967433d4
	access.json	7914cedaca62758212f279689dbbd92f9e6198d185384673d58826a666433ea
	.pcap	37ad98463badd00210c08eb571dbeb4878f9c479a450badb81fe22bcb43a9dde
Moderate Scenario	eve.json	04bf4b7c6c377a415b64a52e52e7b054431336b66895b832484f3e06368f75a2
	access.json	842d4b1ace7a8543228382bf00fbc90c40c45534fe3a1aaac4069a7c3c9796ec
	.pcap	6c29d95b752df79be20cc349d17cc08f08678000ff613a9b858e518784a4e855
Heavy Scenario	eve.json	c676f9fed826b137827752f4957fd94fc81be8f4f66c3f2533615380c24714b
	access.json	bd627316cd9a03538bfbaa51549909e89b95d2b9bbe6d78d7e6c6047a1a08ba
	.pcap	534414daa52e7ebfaf1c5e579a620fcef5afb4b060bde559266acaba69e323f9
Repetitive Scenario	eve.json	16f55d3200f53eee82c6ecda5145000ede966f9db304f98106b07cb10b90addf
	access.json	ac62a3b3c31ec75e56413927d3b9c2abb208c6c234f702009ab06df9e44eaa2
	.pcap	18642250b71851d4d2fc0b2895ce189fd0e795fd1c57a0dd50a0e11663331644
User-agent Scenario	eve.json	0245824d9e97617dc6aae7f173c8b089aefab0a4126a4cf6efde48db2756f81
	access.json	21809bb024e12a2207d9dfecce1065942c854f31213f9a5df476c2668d39a920d
	.pcap	255b50c749f596f39496059b765eddb121fc2cf56a3ecc44c41bb4f9e27a4fbf

Table III presents five sample data collection results from the investigator’s machine, selected from a total of fifteen tested attack scenarios. The data includes eve.json files from Suricata, access.log files from Apache2 as records of web server activity, and packet capture (PCAP) files recorded during the simulation. Each file is accompanied by a SHA256 hash value to ensure data integrity. Integrity is a critical aspect in the context of digital evidence, as even minor modifications can affect its validity. Therefore, an initial verification was conducted using the sha256sum tool to confirm that the data remained intact during the collection process.

C. Analysis

Out of the fifteen testing scenarios conducted, only five representative data samples are displayed in Table III. These examples were selected because they reflect the variations in attack parameters used during the simulations while yielding relatively consistent results.

TABLE IV. SUMMARY OF ATTACK DETECTION BASED ON EVE.JSON LOGS

Scenario	Signature	Number of Alerts	Duration (Seconds)	Start Time	End Time
Light Scenario	SlowLoris.py DoS attempt	3953	178.97	14:28:18	14:31:17

Moderate Scenario	SlowLoris.py DoS attempt	5207	310.9 4	14:36:5 5	14:42:0 6
Heavy Scenario	Possible DDoS attack	1	0	15:07:3 9	15:07:3 9
	SlowLoris.py DoS attempt	10699	606.4 3	15:07:3 9	15:17:4 5
Repetitive Scenario	SlowLoris.py DoS attempt	16034	1400. 01	16:30:3 2	16:53:5 2
User-agent Scenario	SlowLoris.py DoS attempt	2952	304.7 2	17:53:3 7	17:58:4 2

Table IV summarizes the attack detection results based on eve.json logs, showing variations in the number of alerts across different scenarios. In the Heavy Scenario, an alert labeled Possible DDoS attack was detected at the onset of the attack, indicating a sudden surge in connections within a short timeframe. This summary serves as the basis for further analysis of the access.log file, which is presented in Table V.

TABLE V. SUMMARY OF ACCESS.LOG ENTRIES

Scenario	IP Address	Total Hit	Status Codes (count)	Unique User Agents	Start Time	End Time
Light Scenario	192.168.1.9	400	408(350), 400(50)	1	14:28:1 6	14:31:2 0
	192.168.1.9	135 0	408(1348), 400(2)	1	14:36:5 5	14:41:5 9
Moderate Scenario	192.168.1.9	3	200(3)	1	14:37:1 8	14:37:2 0
	192.168.1.9	442 5	408(4201), 400(224)	1	15:07:3 9	15:17:5 3
Repetitive Scenario	192.168.1.9	420	408(4046), 400(154)	1	16:30:3 2	16:53:5 3
	192.168.1.9	899	408(749), 400(150)	25	17:53:3 7	17:58:4 5

Table V shows that in the Moderate Scenario, there are entries with status code 200 and a very low number of hits, indicating normal user activity. This contrasts with other scenarios that are dominated by status code 408, resulting from attack-related traffic.

To strengthen the analysis derived from the eve.json and access.log files, the PCAP file was examined using Wireshark. Fig. 7 presents one representative scenario as an example, as the observed traffic patterns reflect the general characteristics found across all testing scenarios.

Fig. 8. Moderate Scenario PCAP File – Wireshark Display.

Fig. 8 illustrates the Slowloris attack pattern, in which TCP connections are established via a 3-Way Handshake (SYN, SYN-ACK, ACK), followed by the periodic transmission of small packets with the [PSH, ACK] flag to keep the connections alive. This pattern reflects the core characteristic of a Slowloris attack, where a single client opens multiple connections without completing the requests.

Measurement	Captured	Displayed	Marked
Packets	26576	26576 (100.0%)	—
Time span, s	374.478	374.478	—
Average pps	71.0	71.0	—
Average packet size, B	105	105	—
Bytes	2789196	2789196 (100.0%)	0
Average bytes/s	7448	7448	—
Average bits/s	59 k	59 k	—

Fig. 9. Moderate Scenario PCAP File – PCAP File Properties

Fig. displays the traffic statistics of the PCAP file from the attack scenario, showing a total of 26,576 packets over a 6-minute duration with an average packet size of only 105 bytes. The low traffic volume and repeated transmission of small packets reflect the typical pattern of a Slowloris attack. This is further supported by Fig. 9, which illustrates the corresponding TCP stream behavior.

(a) (b)

Fig. 10. Moderate Scenario PCAP File – TCP stream

Fig. 10 illustrates a comparison between failed and successfully completed connections. One example shows an incomplete request that led the server to respond with a 408 Request Timeout, while another connection was normally closed with a 200 OK response. These findings complement the evidence from the eve.json logs, access.log, and PCAP files, all of which are consistent with the characteristics of the Slowloris attack as described in Section II.

D. Report

This stage aims to summarize all procedures carried out in the previous phases. The report is compiled systematically and in detail, covering information related to the incident, including the identities of both the attacker and the victim. This information is presented in a tabular format that outlines the chronology and timestamp details of the attack in a structured manner, as summarized in Table VI.

TABLE VI. REPORT OF COLLECTED ATTACK EVIDENCE

Scenario	Attacker	Victim	Attack Start	End Time
Light Scenario	192.168.1.9	192.168.1.8	20/06/20	20/06/20
			14:28:18	14:31:17
Moderate Scenario	192.168.1.9	192.168.1.8	20/06/20	20/06/20
			14:36:55	14:42:06

Heavy Scenario	192.168.1.9	192.168.1.8	20/06/20 25 15:07:39	20/06/20 25 15:17:45
Repetitive Scenario	192.168.1.9	192.168.1.8	20/06/20 25 16:30:32	20/06/20 25 16:53:52
User-agent Scenario	192.168.1.9	192.168.1.8	20/06/20 25 17:53:37	20/06/20 25 17:58:42

TABLE VII. SUMMARY OF EVIDENCE FROM THE MODERATE SCENARIO

File	Main Findings
eve.js on	A total of 5,207 alerts classified as SlowLoris.py DoS attempt were detected over a duration of 310 seconds, originating from IP address 192.168.1.9 targeting port 80.
access.log	A total of 1,350 HTTP requests were recorded from IP address 192.168.1.9, predominantly resulting in status code 408 (1,348 entries), along with only 2 responses with status code 400. Additionally, entries with status code 200 were observed originating from a different IP address, 192.168.1.2.
.pcap	A total of 26,576 packets were captured over a 6-minute period, with an average packet size of 105 bytes. The connections were initiated using a 3-Way Handshake, followed by incomplete HTTP requests that resulted in status code 408.

Table VII summarizes the evidence from the Moderate Scenario based on three primary sources. The findings from the eve.json file are consistent with the detections presented in Table IV and the Suricata log shown in Fig. 6. The access.log entries support the results outlined in Table V. Meanwhile, the traffic patterns and stream behavior observed in the .pcap file are reinforced by the visual analysis presented in Figs. 7, 8, and 9.

E. Action

The mitigation recommendations against Slowloris attacks, as discussed in Section III-D, include limiting the number of simultaneous connections and implementing temporary blocking of IP addresses identified as potential attackers. These measures aim to effectively halt the attack while minimizing the risk of false positives by allowing further evaluation of suspicious traffic.

F. Evaluation

An evaluation was conducted to assess the effectiveness of the TAARA approach in investigating the Slowloris attack, based on four key aspects commonly applied in digital forensic practice, as follows:

- **Legal Acceptability:** The documentation process using eve.json, access.log, and PCAP files was conducted systematically, supported by accurate timestamps and a valid reporting structure, as shown in Tables III, IV, and VI.
- **Data integrity:** All collected files were verified using SHA256 hashes to ensure no alteration occurred during the acquisition process, as detailed in Table III.
- **Repeatability:** Consistent detection patterns were observed across eve.json, access.log, and PCAP files in terms of alert counts, server responses, and traffic characteristics. This consistency indicates that the

approach is replicable with similar outcomes (see Tables IV, V, and Fig. 8).

- **Effectiveness:** The TAARA approach proved effective in identifying and mapping the characteristics of the Slowloris attack from the initial trigger to the reporting phase, supported by visual evidence (Figs. 6–9) and consolidated forensic data (Table VII).

Based on these four aspects, it can be concluded that the TAARA approach is effective in supporting a valid and accountable digital forensic investigation of the Slowloris attack.

The process, detailed test case and evidence are available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15612669>.

IV. CONCLUSION

This study aimed to implement and evaluate the TAARA (Trigger, Acquire, Analyze, Report, Action) approach in conducting digital forensic investigations of the Slowloris attack, a type of application-layer Denial-of-Service (DoS) attack. The findings demonstrate that TAARA effectively fulfills the core principles of digital forensic standards: the approach ensures legal acceptability through structured documentation and a simplified chain of custody; maintains data integrity via SHA256 hash verification; exhibits result consistency (repeatability) across various testing scenarios; and proves effective in identifying and mapping the behavioral patterns of the attack comprehensively.

These results indicate that TAARA is a reliable and practical framework for digital forensic investigations of subtle and hard-to-detect DoS attacks. Further research is recommended to evaluate the application of this approach to other types of cyber threats, in order to assess the flexibility and generalizability of TAARA across diverse network investigation scenarios.

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